

Synthesis, electrochemical, antimicrobial and superoxide dismutase activity studies on nickel(II) complexes possessing tris(2-aminoethylamine) and N, O donor benzohydrazide ligands

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Abstract : Five new nickel(II) complexes viz. [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ 1; [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ 2; [Ni(tren)(L³)](ClO₄)₂ 3; [Ni(tren)(L⁴)](ClO₄)₂ 4; [Ni(tren)(L⁵)](ClO₄)₂ 5; tren = tris(2-aminoethylamine); L¹ = benzoylhydrazide; L² = N-[(1)-1-(2-methylphenyl)ethylidene]benzohydrazide; L³ = N-[(1)-1-(4-methylphenyl)ethylidene]benzohydrazide; L⁴ = N-[(1)-1-(2-methoxyphenyl)ethylidene]benzohydrazide; L⁵ = N-[(1)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethylidene]benzohydrazide; have been synthesized and characterized by partial elemental analysis, FAB (fast atom bombardment), magnetic susceptibility measurement, electronic absorptions, conductivity measurements and cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements. All the Schiff base ligands (L¹-L⁵) possessing N and O donor sites. Infrared spectra, ligand field spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes 1-5 suggested a distorted octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ion. The redox behavior of the nickel complexes has been studied by cyclic voltammetry and display quasireversible redox wave due to Ni^{II}/Ni^I reduction process. The superoxide dismutase activity reveals that these complexes catalyze the fast disproportionation of superoxide in DMSO solution and IC₅₀ values were evaluated by NBT assay method. *In vitro* antimicrobial study of these complexes has been assayed against two bacterial strains (*Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* sp.) and two fungal strains (*Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* sp.) The antimicrobial results indicated that the nickel complexes displayed better antimicrobial activity as compared to the Schiff bases.

Keywords : Ni^{II} complexes, CV, SOD mimics activity, Schiff bases, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Polyamines are an important class of N donor ligands, particularly for the transition metals¹⁻⁸. Tris(2-aminoethylamine) (tetradentate) are the N donor ligands, used in this work⁹. Recently, Ni-containing superoxide dismutase (NiSOD) was isolated from several streptomyces species¹⁰. The enzymatic activity of NiSOD¹¹, however is on the same high level as that of Cu-ZnSOD at about 10⁹ M⁻¹ s⁻¹ per metal center. The superoxide radical (O₂⁻) is an inevitable byproduct of aerobic metabolism which if not eliminated may cause significant cellular damage; consequently, the superoxide radical has been implicated in numerous medical disorders¹². To avoid such harmful consequences, all oxygen metabolizing organisms process metalloenzymes known as superoxide dismutases (SOD) are dedicated to keep the concentration

of O₂⁻ in controlled low limits thus protecting biological molecules from oxidative damage. These SOD disproportionate the toxic O₂⁻ radical to molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide¹³.

All SOD employ the two-step ping-pong mechanism shown in eqs. (1) and (2), where Ni is a redox active metal center capable of both oxidizing and reducing superoxide :

In the past decade benzoylhydrazones are extensively used in research. They have emerged as an important class of nitrogen-oxygen donor ligands particularly for transition metal ions. The real impetus towards developing in coordination chemistry of these hydrazones have been provided by remarkable biological activities observed for

these compounds which has been shown to be related to their metal complex activity. Johnson *et al.*¹⁴, have found that benzoylhydrazone and their derivative have strong insecticidal activity against various insects. In continuation of our work¹⁵ on Schiff base and their metal(II) complexes, we here describes the synthesis, electrochemical, antimicrobial and SOD activity of octahedral nickel(II) complexes namely [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ **1**; [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ **2**; [Ni(tren)(L³)](ClO₄)₂ **3**; [Ni(tren)(L⁴)](ClO₄)₂ **4**; [Ni(tren)(L⁵)](ClO₄)₂ **5**. Tris(2-aminoethylamine) is a tetradentate chelating ligand which having N₄ donor site whereas all the Schiff base ligands (L¹-L⁵) possessing N and O donor atom. The SOD activities have been measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

NiCl₂.6H₂O, tris(2-aminoethylamine), sodium perchlorate (Across Chemicals) were used as supplied. All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Elemental analyses were performed on an Elementar Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer. FAB Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX102/DA 6000 mass spectrometer/data system using xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. UV-Visible recording spectrophotometer UV-160 in quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer in the 4000–600 cm⁻¹ region. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a BAS-100 Epsilon electrochemical analyzer having an electrochemical cell with a three-electrode system. Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode. Molar conductivities of freshly prepared 2 × 10⁻³ M of acetonitrile solutions were measured on a Systronics conductivity TDS meter 308. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger¹⁶. In general, 400 μL sample to be assayed was added to a solution containing 2.1 ml of 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and 1 ml of 56 μM of alkaline DMSO solution was added while string. The absorbance was then monitored at 540 nm against a sample

prepared under similar condition except NaOH was absent in DMSO. The *in vitro* antibacterial activities of these complexes were tested using paper disc diffusion method¹⁷ the chosen strains were G (+) *Streptococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The liquid medium containing the bacterial subcultures was autoclaved for 20 min at 121 °C and at 15 lb pressure before inoculation. The bacteria were then cultured for 24 h at 36 °C in an incubator. The antifungal activity of the compounds have been evaluated against *Aspergillus* sp. and *Pencillium* sp. by the Radial Growth Method¹⁸ using czapek's agar medium. The compounds were added directly with the medium in 5, 10 and 15 mM concentrations.

Synthesis of L²-L⁵ :

The Schiff bases L²-L⁵ were prepared by standard literature procedure^{9,10} and recrystallized from ethanol or methanol. A methanol solution of benzoylhydrazide (10 mmol, 1.36 g) was stirred with (10 mL) of 2-methylacetophenone (10 mmol, 1.34 g), 4-methylacetophenone (10 mmol, 1.34 g), 2-methoxyacetophenone (10 mmol, 1.50 g), 4-methoxyacetophenone (10 mmol, 1.50 g) respectively. The precipitate was obtained, washed with cold methanol and diethyl ether, dried in air and stored in a CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield varied at the range 80–90%. Analytical data of Schiff base ligands (L¹-L⁵) are presented in Table 1.

*Synthesis of [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ **1**; [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ **2**; [Ni(tren)(L³)](ClO₄)₂ **3**; [Ni(tren)(L⁴)](ClO₄)₂ **4**; [Ni(tren)(L⁵)](ClO₄)₂ **5** :*

To a MeOH solution (20 mL) of NiCl₂.CH₂O (1.0 mmol, g), a MeOH solution (10 mL) of tren (1.0 mmol, 0.146 g) was added with stirring for 30 min at 25 °C. To the above reaction mixture have, a methanolic solution (20 mL) of L¹ (1.0 mmol, 0.136 g), L² (1.0 mmol, 0.252 g), L³ (1.0 mmol, 0.252 g), L⁴ (1.0 mmol, 0.268 g), L⁵ (1.0 mmol, 1.50 g) respectively and NaClO₄ (2.0 mmol, 0.25 g) was added for another 30 min at RT. After completion of the reaction a light green or red micro crystalline solid deposited was collected by filtration and washed with methanol. The obtained solid was dried in air and stored in a CaCl₂ desiccator at RT. Yield varied at the range 75–85%. Analytical data of synthesized nickel(II) complexes **1-5** are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands (L¹-L⁵) and their nickel(II) complexes

Ligand (L ¹ -L ⁵) and compounds	Empirical formula	Analytical data (%) : Calcd. (Found)			FAB-mass (<i>m/z</i>) (%)	
		C	H	N	Calcd.	Found
L ¹	C ₇ H ₈ N ₂ O	61.69 (61.67)	5.87 (5.85)	20.56 (20.54)	136.1	136
L ²	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	76.09 (76.07)	6.34 (6.32)	11.09 (11.07)	252.3	252
L ³	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	76.09 (76.07)	6.34 (6.32)	11.09 (11.07)	252.3	252
L ⁴	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	71.55 (71.53)	5.96 (5.94)	10.43 (10.41)	268.3	268
L ⁵	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	71.55 (71.53)	5.96 (5.94)	10.43 (10.41)	268.3	268
[Ni(tren)(L ¹)](ClO ₄) ₂ 1	C ₁₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ NiCl ₂ O ₉	28.93 (28.90)	4.82 (4.80)	15.38 (15.36)	539.1	539
[Ni(tren)(L ²)](ClO ₄) ₂ 2	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ NiCl ₂ O ₉	40.34 (40.32)	5.19 (5.18)	12.83 (12.81)	654.2	654
[Ni(tren)(L ³)](ClO ₄) ₂ 3	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ NiCl ₂ O ₉	40.34 (40.32)	5.19 (5.18)	12.83 (12.81)	654.2	654
[Ni(tren)(L ⁴)](ClO ₄) ₂ 4	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ NiCl ₂ O ₁₀	39.32 (39.30)	5.06 (5.04)	12.50 (12.48)	671.2	671
[Ni(tren)(L ⁵)](ClO ₄) ₂ 5	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ NiCl ₂ O ₁₀	39.32 (39.30)	5.06 (5.04)	12.50 (12.48)	671.2	671

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The present complexes prepared in high yield by reacting nickel(II) salt with tris(2-aminoethylamine) and L¹-L⁵ ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio to give complexes of general composition [Cu(A)(B)]. The reactions proceed in the following manner (Scheme 1).

where, A = tren, B = L¹-L⁵ and X = ClO₄. The Schiff base ligands was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of benzoylhydrazine and 2-methylacetophenone, 4-methylacetophenone, 2-methoxyacetophenone, 4-methoxyacetophenone respectively, in ethanol for 3 h. The complexes are insoluble in water, cold ethanol, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and diethyl ether but are fairly soluble in hot ethanol, DMF, and DMSO. All the complexes decompose between 160 and 280 °C. Very low values of molar conductance (2.45–7.22 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature indicate that they are non-electrolytes¹⁹. There were characterized by microanalysis, FAB⁺ spectrometry and then by electrochemical and spectroscopic techniques.

Magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ **1**; [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ **2**; [Ni(tren)(L³)](ClO₄)₂ **3**; [Ni(tren)(L⁴)](ClO₄)₂ **4**; [Ni(tren)(L⁵)](ClO₄)₂ **5** were 3.10, 2.95, 3.06, 2.98, and 3.12 B.M., respectively. These

were as expected for spin-free *d*⁸ systems and lie within the range normally found for nickel(II) complexes having octahedral geometry^{20,21}. The electronic spectrum of complexes **1** shows three strong absorption's and one weak absorptions, characteristics of regular octahedral Ni^{II}. These bands may be assigned to the three spin allowed transitions^{22,23} and the fourth may be considered as a charge transfer band. This complex shows three strong absorptions and one weak absorptions [³A_{2g}→³T_{2g} (10205 cm⁻¹ v₁), ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (F) (15625 cm⁻¹ v₂), ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (P) (28570 cm⁻¹ v₃), characteristics of regular octahedral²⁴ nickel(II) (Fig. 1). The electronic spectral data of nickel(II) complexes **1-5** were shown in Table 2. Remaining complexes show similar characteristics features. However, band shapes and positions (assigned on the basis of *Oh* symmetry) and the *D*_q (ligand field parameter) and β (Racah parameter) values are in the range found for octahedral coordinated nickel(II) ion with a ligand set for four N and two O atoms^{25,26}.

Infrared study :

The FT-IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on KBr discs in the 4000–6000 cm⁻¹. IR spectrum of the ligands (L¹-L⁵) exhibited the most characteristics bands at 1603–1641 cm⁻¹ v(C=N, azomethine nitrogen), 1268–1275 cm⁻¹ v(C-O) bonds. This is confirmed by the bands in the range 465–474 cm⁻¹ which confirms the v(Ni-N) band. Medium bands in the region 3450–3190 cm⁻¹, are assigned to the N-H vibrations²⁷, are assigned in the region 1603–1630 and of 460–490 cm⁻¹. A strong band, observed at *ca.* 1205–1310 cm⁻¹ is assigned to coordination through phenolic oxygen²⁸. The IR data of ligands

Scheme 1. Synthesis of nickel(II) complexes 1-5.

and their nickel(II) complexes showed that the Schiff bases were coordinated to the metal ion in a bidentate manner (N, O) whereas tren was bound as N_4 donor atoms. In addition, the IR spectra of the complexes containing perchlorate anions were dominated by the very strong stretching vibrations characteristic of ClO_4 groups²⁹ (1086–1112 and 618–622 cm^{-1}) in all the cases, in agreement with their non-coordinating character. Vibrations at 440–480 cm^{-1} (weak) (and expected below 400 cm^{-1} ; out of our measuring limit) can be attributed to Ni-O and Ni-N vibration²⁹.

Cyclic voltammetric measurements :

The electrochemistry of the present nickel(II) complexes was investigated by cyclic voltammetry in DMSO solutions possessing 0.1 M NaClO_4 as supporting electrolyte at platinum working electrode. The electrochemical response of the complexes was complicated by adsorption of the reduction products at the electrode surface, especially at the platinum working electrode. The potential and currents of adsorption peaks depends strongly on the experimental conditions, therefore a careful choice of optimal parameters was necessary to minimize such

Fig. 1. The UV-Vis spectra ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) of $[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^1)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$.

effects. The more information of CV results of these complexes are available in Table 3 and the representative cyclic voltammogram of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^1)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ **1** is depicted in Fig. 2. The redox behavior of all complexes with L^1 - L^5 Schiff base ligands are quite similar. The cyclic voltammograms of these complexes exhibit an irreversible wave that can be assigned to a $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}-\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}$ redox process³⁰. Constancy of E° shows that in all cases both

Fig. 2. The cyclic voltammogram ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) of $[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^1)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ at NaClO_4 as supporting electrolyte (scan rate 100 mV/s).

peaks are complementary to each other. In all cases the peak potential differences increases as scan rate increases. In the redox process that the $\text{N}^{\text{II}}/\text{N}^{\text{I}}$ potentials are mainly associated with the affinity between the donors and N^{II} ions. The cathodic peak potential differences increases as the scan rate is increased. The peak current ratio $I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$ is

Table 2. Electronic spectra, D_q , β , B and β° of the octahedral Ni^{II} complexes (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) complexes

	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (ν_1)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3)	ν_2/ν_3	$10D_q$	β	β (cm^{-1})	β°
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^1)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 1	10205	15625	28570	1.53	10205	0.869	905	13.10
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 2	10275	15885	26840	1.54	10275	0.762	793	23.80
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^3)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 3	10275	15885	26840	1.54	10275	0.762	793	23.80
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 4	12270	18145	28740	1.47	1227	0.65	672	35
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^5)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 5	12270	18145	28740	1.47	1227	0.65	672	35

$15 B = (\nu_2 + \nu_3) - 3\nu_1$; $\beta = B/B_0$ [B_0 (free ion) = 1030]; $\beta^\circ = 1 - \beta \times 100$.

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data for 1 mM solution of the nickel(II) complexes in DMSO containing 0.1 M NaClO_4 as supporting electrolytes

Complexes	Scan rate (mV/s)	E_{pc} (mv)	I_{pc} (μA)	E_{pa} (mv)	I_{pa} (μA)	ΔE_p	E°	$I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$ (μA)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^1)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 1	100	-656	1.573	-433	0.715	223	-544	0.45
	200	-680	2.225	-409	1.012	271	-544	0.45
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 2	100	-711	1.597	-475	0.961	236	-593	0.602
	200	-738	1.980	-448	1.214	290	-593	0.613
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^3)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 3	100	-711	1.597	-475	0.961	236	-593	0.602
	200	-738	1.980	-448	1.214	290	-593	0.613
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 4	100	-668	1.404	-385	0.585	283	-526	0.42
	200	-693	1.976	-360	0.831	333	-526	0.42
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{L}^5)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ 5	100	-668	1.404	-385	0.585	283	-526	0.42
	200	-693	1.976	-360	0.831	333	-526	0.42

less than unity showing that the electron transfer reaction is followed by a chemical reaction (EC mechanism)³¹.

Superoxide dismutase activity :

Biological activities (SOD mimetic activities) of the Ni^{II} complexes have also been measured. The SOD mimetic activities of the present complexes were examined by the NBT assay following kinetically the reduction of NBT to MF⁺ at 565 nm. Superoxide was enzymatically supplied from alkaline DMSO. The count fraction causing 50% inhibition of NBT reduction is called IC₅₀. Concentration equivalent to one unit of SOD activity (IC₅₀ values), together with the IC₅₀ values of native SOD are given in Table 4 and Fig. 3. Obtained results of IC₅₀ for present complexes are remain in the range 50 ± 5 μm. The observed IC₅₀ values of the present complexes are comparable with the various reported values for the Ni^{II}

Fig. 3. Superoxide dismutase activity of [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂.

Antimicrobial activity against pathogens :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of the synthesized nickel complexes against two selected bacteria viz. *E. coli* and *Streptococcus aureus* pathogens were determined. Any chemotherapeutic agent reduce the growth of microbes by microbial and micro static mechanisms. Antibacterial assessment of the complexes was tested as a function of concentration of these complexes and results are presented in Table 5. These activities were determined at three concentrations i.e. 5, 10, and 15 mM of each compound in DMSO. On comprising the biological activities of Schiff base ligands (L¹-L⁵) and their metal complexes with those lower concentration of a standard bactericide antibiotic (chloramphenicol) and fungicide (Miconazole) was shown that the nickel complexes had moderate activity as compared to the standard but all the complexes more active than their respective ligands. Each

Table 4. Superoxide dismutase activity of some Ni^{II} complexes 1-5

Sr. No.	Complexes	IC ₅₀ (μ mol dm ⁻³)	Ref.
1.	[Ni(BPSE)]BF ₄	65	33
2.	[Ni(5-BST)(CH ₃ OH)]ClO ₄	48	33
3.	[Ni(tren)(phen)](ClO ₄) ₂	40	32
4.	Native SOD	0.04	15
5.	[Ni(HL)(PMDT)]BF ₄	58	15
6.	[Ni(tren)(bipy)](ClO ₄) ₂	48	32
7.	[Ni(SAA)(PMDT)].2H ₂ O	43	32
8.	[Ni(tren)(L ¹)](ClO ₄) ₂ 1	55	This work
9.	[Ni(tren)(L ²)](ClO ₄) ₂ 2	45	This work
10.	[Ni(tren)(L ³)](ClO ₄) ₂ 3	54	This work
11.	[Ni(tren)(L ⁴)](ClO ₄) ₂ 4	46	This work
12.	[Ni(tren)(L ⁵)](ClO ₄) ₂ 5	53	This work

complexes^{32,33}, but are less active than the native SOD. The good activities of complexes may be attributed to the flexible tren and L¹-L⁵ ligands which is able to accommodate the geometrical change from Ni^{II} to Ni^I, which are proposed to be easily substituted by the substrate O₂⁻ in the catalytic process, just like the O₂⁻, in place of H₂O bound to copper site in the mechanism of dismutation of O₂⁻ by native SOD. Complex **1-5** show lower IC₅₀, and exhibits higher SOD activity than other Ni^{II} complexes except for two systems including native SOD so for reported³². The catalytic activity of Ni-SOD³³, is on the same high level as that of Cu, Zn-SOD at about 10⁹ M⁻¹ per metal center.

Table 5. Antibacterial activity screening data of Ni^{II} complexes

Complexes (mM)	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>Streptococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
[Ni(tren)(L ¹)](ClO ₄) ₂ 1		
5	7	9
10	10	12
15	12	14
[Ni(tren)(L ²)](ClO ₄) ₂ 2		
5	8	13
10	10	16
15	16	20

experiment was performed in triplicate. The susceptibility of certain strains of bacteria towards the present Ni^{II} complexes were determined by measuring the size of inhibition diameter. The growth inhibitory effects were observed against bacterial pathogens *E. coli* and *Streptococcus aureus*. Both the bacteria are pathogens for humans, which causes dysentery and food poisoning, respectively. They inhibited the bacterial growth up to 14–18% at 15 mM whereas others have poor antibacterial activity. The area of zone of inhibition is less in the concentration of 5 mM, in both micro-organisms and more in 15 mM concentration (Fig. 4). This kind of observation is suggestive of that these complexes are effective against both pathogens. Complexes **1** and **2** have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus*. Both complexes show lower activity than the known antibiotic chloramphenicol with [Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ **1** being more active than [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ **2**. The higher inhibition zone of the nickel complexes than those of the ligands can be explained based on Overtone concept³⁵ and Tweedy's chelation theory³⁶. Among fungal species two isolates were taken into consideration and were *Aspergillus* and

Fig. 4. Antibacterial activity of [Ni(tren)(L¹)] **1**.

Penicillium sp. The zone of inhibition of these compounds against those fungi was recorded in Fig. 5. Similar trends were observed as in the case of bacteria. It was noted that *Penicillium sp.* was highly susceptible against complex **1**. Another fungi *Aspergillus sp.* showed least effectiveness against complex **2**; but comparatively more susceptible

Fig. 5. Antifungal activity of [Ni(tren)(L¹)] **1**.

towards **1**. It is observed from these tests that metal chelates have a higher activity than the free ligand. Similar antimicrobial results were also reported by Mishra *et al.*^{37,38}. These complexes also disturb the respiratory processes of the cell and thus block the synthesis of the protein, which restricts further growth of the organism.

Conclusion

[Ni(tren)(L¹)](ClO₄)₂ **1**; [Ni(tren)(L²)](ClO₄)₂ **2**; [Ni(tren)(L³)](ClO₄)₂ **3**; [Ni(tren)(L⁴)](ClO₄)₂ **4**; [Ni(tren)(L⁵)](ClO₄)₂ **5**; were synthesized and characterized by different physico-chemical and spectroscopic techniques. Superoxide dismutase activity of present complexes in the increasing order **1** > **3** > **5** > **4** > **2** where it appears that the inclusion of N, O donor ligands reduce the SOD activity. The magnetic moment values

and spectroscopic data show the paramagnetic nature of the nickel(II) centres and all complexes adopt distorted octahedral MN_5O environments, coordination through four N atoms of one tren and one bidentate N, O donor (L^1-L^5) Schiff base ligands. Complexes **1** and **2** have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus*. The antimicrobial data shows that the nickel complexes were more biologically active compared to the parent Schiff base ligands against all the tested pathogenic species. Such species may assist in the search for some novel chemotherapeutic to answer the emerging problem of drug resistance in health sciences.

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